

GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource:

Guide on equity, diversity and inclusion (EDI) in research assessment

Actionable version

Definition

This guide discusses equity, diversity, and inclusion (EDI) as an ethical foundation of research and research assessment (RA). EDI is about ensuring that research environments are safe, fair, and inclusive for individuals across gender, race, ability, career stage, geography, and culture. Embedding EDI in organizational RA policies reduces bias, strengthens integrity, and fosters innovation by embracing diverse perspectives and career paths.

Relevant SCOPE stages

This resource is most relevant for SCOPE stages:

- Options for evaluating: Expanding assessment criteria to recognise diverse outputs, roles, and career paths.
- Probe deeply: Critically examining processes to identify and mitigate biases in recruitment, promotion, and evaluation.

When and how to use

Use this guide when:

- Designing or updating assessment frameworks to include EDI principles.
- Recruiting and promoting staff, ensuring open, transparent, and inclusive processes.
- Evaluating researchers' contributions, especially those with non-linear or interdisciplinary careers.
- Developing institutional policies to align with e.g. ARRA (Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment) and international guidelines.

How to use:

- Broaden recognition → Value a range of outputs (e.g., data, software, mentoring, engagement, multilingual publications).
- Apply fair criteria → Ensure criteria respect disciplinary, career stage, and sectoral differences.
- Ensure accessibility → Address language and disability-related barriers; promote multilingual and accessible outputs.
- Promote inclusivity → Ensure diverse representation in panels, committees, and leadership roles.
- Review regularly → Monitor progress on EDI and update assessment frameworks accordingly.

Guidance

- Principles to embed: Transparency, fairness, inclusivity, accountability.
- Mitigate bias: Train evaluators, use diverse panels, adopt narrative CVs, and recognise non-linear career paths.
- Recognise diverse activities: Reward collaboration, societal engagement, peer review, mentoring, and team science.
- Support accessibility: Adopt Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) and promote multilingual publishing.
- Recruit inclusively: Advertise openly, ensure selection committees are diverse, and align processes with EDI values.
- Everyday practices: Appoint EDI officers, integrate EDI into job descriptions, maintain institutional action plans, and monitor outcomes.

Further reading

- ARRA Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (2022): <https://coara.eu>
- SCOPE Framework (INORMS, 2023): <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>
- UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science (2021): <https://doi.org/10.54677/MNMH8546>
- NWO (2019) Room for everyone's talent: <https://www.nwo.nl/en/position-paper-room-for-everyones-talent>
- Helsinki Initiative on Multilingualism: <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7887059>
- Web Accessibility Initiative (WAI): <https://www.w3.org/WAI/>

